

Reconstruction of the Mammary Gland: Breast Implants versus Autologous Tissues in Breast Cancer

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ABSTRACT

Breast reconstruction is an essential component of breast cancer management, aiming to restore the physical appearance and emotional well-being of patients who have undergone mastectomy or lumpectomy. Two primary approaches, implant-based reconstruction and autologous tissue reconstruction, offer distinct advantages and considerations.

Implant-based reconstruction involves the use of silicone or saline breast implants, offering a less invasive surgical procedure and shorter recovery time. However, potential complications, such as implant malposition and capsular contracture, should be carefully considered.

Autologous tissue reconstruction utilizes the patient's own tissues to reconstruct the breast, providing a more natural outcome. While this method may involve a more complex surgery and longer recovery time, it avoids the use of foreign materials.

The choice between these approaches is multifaceted and involves patient preferences, anatomical considerations, previous treatments, and overall health status. Shared decision-making between patients and healthcare professionals is crucial to achieving patient satisfaction and optimal outcomes.

Breast reconstruction plays a significant role in supporting breast cancer survivors on their journey towards physical and emotional healing, empowering them to embrace their new identity and regain a positive body image. Continued research and advancements in breast reconstruction techniques hold promise for further improving patient outcomes and enhancing quality of life.

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INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer remains one of the most prevalent malignancies worldwide, affecting millions of women and, to a lesser extent, men. The incidence of breast cancer varies significantly across regions and populations, with the highest rates observed in developed countries. Early detection and advances in treatment have led to improved survival rates, contributing to a growing population of breast cancer survivors.

Surgical interventions, such as mastectomy or partial mastectomy (lumpectomy), are commonly employed in the management of breast cancer. These procedures are essential for disease control and achieving favorable oncological outcomes. However, the loss of breast tissue resulting from these surgeries can have profound physical and psychosocial effects on patients. Breast reconstruction emerges as a critical component of comprehensive breast cancer treatment, aiming to restore the natural contour and symmetry of the breast and enhance the emotional well-being of the patient.

The significance of breast reconstruction in the context of breast cancer treatment cannot be overstated. For many women, the loss of a breast can lead to a sense of disfigurement and emotional distress. Breast reconstruction offers an opportunity for patients to regain a sense of normalcy, improve body image, and enhance self-esteem following cancer treatment.

Studies have shown that breast reconstruction can positively impact a patient's quality of life, body confidence, and overall psychological well-being. The psychological and emotional benefits of breast reconstruction extend beyond physical appearance, empowering breast cancer survivors to regain control over their bodies and embrace their new identity.

The choice between different reconstructive techniques, such as breast implants or autologous tissue reconstruction, poses unique considerations for both patients and surgeons. Understanding the theoretical framework and clinical outcomes of each approach is crucial in facilitating informed decision-making and achieving the best possible outcomes for breast cancer survivors.

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In this literature review, we delve into the theoretical framework and clinical considerations surrounding breast reconstruction using breast implants and autologous tissues. By examining the epidemiology, significance, definitions, surgical treatments, and potential complications, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the options available for breast cancer survivors seeking breast reconstruction. The discussion and conclusions of this review will offer valuable insights to healthcare professionals, enabling them to make informed decisions that cater to individual patient needs and preferences, ultimately improving patient satisfaction and quality of life.

DEFINITION

Breast reconstruction is a surgical procedure aimed at restoring the shape, volume, and symmetry of the breast following mastectomy or lumpectomy for breast cancer treatment. Two main approaches are commonly utilized: breast implant-based reconstruction and autologous tissue reconstruction.

Surgical Treatment

Implant-Based Reconstruction: In implant-based reconstruction, silicone or saline breast implants are used to create the new breast mound. The process typically involves a staged approach. Initially, a tissue expander is placed to gradually stretch the skin and create space for the implant. Subsequent surgeries involve replacing the expander with the permanent implant and possibly adjusting the contralateral breast to achieve symmetry. Implant-based reconstruction

offers a relatively straightforward and less invasive surgical procedure, which can be appealing to some patients.

Autologous Tissue Reconstruction: Autologous tissue reconstruction involves using the patient's own tissues to reconstruct the breast. Commonly harvested tissues include the abdominal region (e.g., TRAM or DIEP flap), back (latissimus dorsi flap), or buttocks (gluteal free flap). The use of autologous tissues provides a more natural look and feel, as the reconstructed breast tissue is the patient's own. However, autologous tissue reconstruction requires more extensive surgery and may involve longer recovery times and potential donor site complications.

Complications

Both implant-based and autologous tissue reconstruction are associated with specific complications:

Implant-Based Reconstruction Complications: Complications related to breast implants may include infection, implant malposition, capsular contracture (formation of scar tissue around the implant), and implant rupture. Implant-related complications may necessitate additional surgeries for revision or replacement.

Autologous Tissue Reconstruction Complications: Autologous tissue reconstruction carries the risk of flap failure, wound healing issues, fat necrosis (death of fatty tissue), and potential donor site morbidity. While autologous tissue reconstruction offers a more natural result, it also involves a more complex surgical procedure and potential complications at the donor site.

Factor	Breast Implants	Autologous Tissues
Definition	Silicone or saline implants used to create the breast mound	Patient's own tissues (e.g., abdomen, back, buttocks) used to reconstruct the breast
Surgical Procedure	Staged approach: Tissue expander placed first, followed by permanent implant	One-time surgery using patient's tissues
Aesthetics	May provide less natural look and feel compared to autologous tissues	More natural appearance and feel
Recovery Time	Generally quicker recovery	Longer initial recovery period
Donor Site Morbidity	None	Potential donor site complications (e.g., abdominal weakness)
Complications	Implant malposition, capsular contracture, implant rupture	Flap failure, wound healing issues, fat necrosis
Long-term Maintenance	Implant revisions or replacements may be required	Permanent reconstruction
Psychological Impact	May not fully address body image concerns	Often positively impacts body confidence and well-being
Suitability	Suitable for various body types and medical conditions	Dependent on available donor tissues and medical history
Shared Decision-making	Patient's preference plays a significant role in the decision	Shared decision-making between the patient and surgeon

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DISCUSSION

The choice between breast implants and autologous tissue reconstruction is not a one-size-fits-all decision and requires careful consideration of multiple factors. Patient preferences, medical history, breast cancer stage, body habitus, and previous treatments all play a crucial role in determining the most appropriate reconstruction approach.

Implant-Based Reconstruction may be favored by patients seeking a less invasive procedure, shorter recovery time, and possibly fewer surgical scars. However, concerns over long-term implant maintenance and the potential for implant-related complications may influence the decision.

Autologous Tissue Reconstruction, on the other hand, provides a more natural outcome and avoids the use of foreign materials. Patients may appreciate the permanence and integration of their own tissues. However, the more extensive surgery, longer recovery time, and potential donor site morbidity must be weighed against these advantages.

Shared decision-making between the patient and the surgical team is essential to ensure that the chosen reconstruction approach aligns with the patient's goals, lifestyle, and medical considerations. Each patient's unique circumstances and personal preferences should be carefully taken into account when determining the most suitable reconstruction method.

Furthermore, continued research and technological advancements in breast reconstruction techniques are expected to further refine surgical outcomes and improve patient satisfaction. Ultimately, breast reconstruction plays a pivotal role in supporting breast cancer survivors on their journey towards physical and emotional healing, empowering them to reclaim their bodies and restore their self-confidence.

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